

Molecular Dynamics-derived Mode I Traction Laws for Crystalline UHMWPE Fibrils

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Celebrating 50 Years

Overall Problem Statement - UHMWPE

Goal: Understand how **consolidation process variables** (temp., pres., and time) can be used to **control composite microstructure** (*reduce voids, minimize filament damage*) in order to **improve composite performance** (*reduce weight, maximize energy absorption*).

Hypothesis: *Void content reduction will increase tensile strength until a plateau strength is achieved*

- Plateau strength is governed by the remaining critical defects at lower length scales
- Process optimization provides a route to control critical defects and increase plateau strength
- Excessive consolidation pressure may damage fibers at all length scales and reduce strength

Research Method: Molecular Dynamics (MD)

- MD simulations are widely used to study the structures and properties of materials at the nanoscale.
- MD solves Newton's equation of motion ($F=ma$), and it is much faster than QM and DFT simulations.
- Atomic interactions are described by interatomic potential fields.
- Selection of the proper potential is very important for accurate predictions of properties.
- We use AIREBO-M (developed for hydrocarbons) to model polyethylene.
- Used LAMMPS, OVITO.

Multiscale Modeling: MD Informed FEA

MD

Chain ends

Misaligned interfaces

Voids at interfaces

Collapsed voids & wavy chains

Amorphous regions

FE

Collapse of voids
between oriented fibrils

- MD simulations predict the 3D stress-strain response and cohesive traction laws for crystalline/amorphous PE.
- These predictions consider various factors, such as defects, strain rate, molecular weight, transverse pressure from impact, and temperature on progressive failure.
- The MD results serve as input for bridging length scales in FE.

Mode-I Traction Laws of UHMWPE Crystals

Mode I Loading

FEA

Collapse of voids between oriented fibrils

Selection of Interphase Thickness

Mode-I Traction-Separation Response

Misaligned a-b Interfaces

Mode-I Response of Misaligned a-b Interfaces

- Critical separation is between ~ 0.3 to 0.4 nm.
- The interfacial properties remain unaffected by voids (the relatively small size of the voids).
- The relatively weak van der Waals forces allow the chains to easily readjust themselves to minimize any emerging stress concentration.

Park–Paulino–Roesler (PPR) cohesive zone model

Park *et al.* J. Mech. Phys. Solids 57 (2009)

$$\Psi(\Delta_n) = \Gamma_n \left(1 - \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right)^\alpha \left(\frac{m}{\alpha} + \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right)^m + \Phi_n$$

where, Γ_n is the Mode I energy constant; Δ_n is the normal separation distance; δ_n is the critical separation distance; α is the shape parameter and m is the non-dimensional exponent.

$$T_n(\Delta_n) = \frac{\Gamma_n}{\delta_n} \left[m \left(1 - \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right)^\alpha \left(\frac{m}{\alpha} + \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right)^{m-1} - \alpha \left(1 - \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{m}{\alpha} + \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right)^m \right]$$

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